

Tribological Behavior of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Metals

A. Kitamura¹⁾, T. Teraoka²⁾, R. Sagara³⁾

- 1) Toray Industries, Inc., Pioneering R & D Laboratories, 2-1, Sonoyama 3-chome, Otsu, Shiga 520, Japan
- 2) Japanese National Railways, Railway Technical Research Institute, Chemistry Laboratory, 2-8-38 Hikari-cho, Kokubunji, Tokyo 185, Japan
- 3) Japan Powder Metallurgy Inc., Research Laboratory, Kurusuno, Kitsunozuka-cho, Yamashina, Kyoto 607, Japan

ABSTRACT

Friction and wear properties of randomly oriented carbon fiber/Cu-Sn matrix composites were investigated. Wear rate and coefficient of friction decreased with increase of carbon fiber content of the composite without current. When current was applied, however, wear rate increased in much higher order even with high content of carbon fiber at high velocity. To lower this wear rate of the composite, it is necessary to improve adhesion strength between carbon fiber and matrix metal. Titanium addition to matrix metal was most effective to improve adhesion by formation of titanium carbide at the interface between carbon fiber and matrix metal. Spark resistivity was improved by this titanium carbide formation and wear rate of the composite extremely decreased under current condition.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced metal is attractive not only for structural material but also for sliding one (1),(2),(3). M.F. Amateau, et al. have studied tribological behavior of carbon fiber reinforced metal composites. They reported that the composite with low modulus PAN-based fiber had the lowest wear and friction rate (4). For carbon fiber/Cu-Sn matrix composites, both friction coefficient and wear rate decreased as the amount of tin in the matrix increased (5). The best frictional behavior was obtained when the fibers were oriented perpendicular to the sliding surface (5),(6),(7).

J.M. Casstevens, et al. reported the results of high speed dry friction experiments using carbon fiber/Cu-Sn matrix composites under current condition. They said that wear rates of the composite material with current were very much higher than those without current.

We studied some wear and friction behaviors of randomly oriented carbon fiber/Cu-Sn (bronze) matrix composites at high speed without lubricants. The way for improvement to this high wear rate of composites under current conditions are discussed here.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

The composite materials used in this study were prepared by the following three steps. In the first step low modulus high strength carbon fibers (Torayca T300) were electrically plated with copper of about $0.8 \mu\text{m}$ thickness. In the second step plated carbon fibers were cut into two or three mm. Then they were mixed with metal powders sufficiently. The metal powders were copper and tin. Moreover in some cases carbide former metal powders were added. The total amount of plated copper plus added copper powder versus added tin powder amount was 9 : 1. Carbon fiber volume content of the composite was varied from 15 to 55 % by the amount of added copper and tin powder.

In the third step mixed materials were hot-pressed in vacuum at 750°C under 40 MPa for a period of 30 min. A cross section of the copper plated carbon fiber is shown in Fig. 1. A typical microstructure of the carbon fiber/Cu-Sn matrix composite used in this study is shown in Fig. 2.

Apparatus

The test apparatus consists of a band of hard copper ring (5 mm width and 1000 mm diameter) set around the steel rotor. The test specimen, having $90 \times 25 \times 10 \text{ mm}$, was pressed on the hard copper ring which was traversed 60 mm width one time for one rotor turning. Friction and wear tests were performed in air at linear sliding speed up to 200 Km/hr (56 m/sec). The normal force employed was 50 N. The friction and normal force on specimen were measured by strain gauge force transducer. The temperature of bulk specimen was measured by a thermocouple placed inside the specimen at 5 mm distance from the friction surface.

Three running conditions were employed. The first condition was continuous 30 min contact. The second condition was cycles of 5 sec contact followed by 5 sec non-contact for a total running time of 30 min. The third condition was cycles of 1 sec contact followed by 1 sec non-contact for a total running time of 30 min. For the current-carrying experiments 100A and 200A (DC) current were applied. After running, the specimen was removed and weighed to determine weight loss. From the density of the composite, the weight loss was converted into volume wear per test load and length of sliding ($\text{mm}^3/\text{Kg}\cdot\text{mm}$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 3 shows wear rate for the carbon fiber/Cu-Sn matrix composites tested as a function of carbon fiber content under condition of cycles of 5 sec contact followed by 5 sec non-contact. It is apparent that wear rate decreased with increase of fiber content. When current was applied, wear rate of the composite increased. At high sliding velocity, wear rate increased was much higher than at low sliding velocity. Fig. 4 shows that coefficient of friction and heat generation in the composite became lower as fiber content increased. Wear rate of the composite under the condition of continuous 30 min contact is shown in Fig. 5. Wear rate decreased with increase of sliding velocity when no current was passed through. But when current was passed through, wear rate drastically increased by about two orders of magnitude, reaching a maximum value of $2 \times 10^5 \text{ mm}^3/\text{Kg}\cdot\text{mm}$ at 100 Km/hr (28 m/sec) and 200 Km/hr (56 m/sec). We believe that these behaviors are due to the following reasons. Carbon fiber reinforced metal composite have good wear resistivity owing to the good lubricating property of carbon fiber. But under current condition, the composite gets heat of sparks. Eventually the sliding surface of the composite begins to melt. Carbon fiber adhesion strength with matrix metal is very poor, so that carbon fiber flies away from the composite when the matrix metal melts. At high sliding velocity, heavy sparks occur by the bouncing increase. Therefore wear rate of the composite is very much higher under current conditions than without current, and increases with increase of sliding velocity. To improve this high wear rate under current condition, it is necessary to strengthen the adhesion strength

between carbon fiber and matrix metal.

We tried to form carbide at the interface between carbon fiber and matrix metal. Carbon fiber plated with copper by 0.8 μm thick was cut into two or three mm, and copper and tin powders were added. Moreover, carbide former metal powder was added and mixed sufficiently. The mixture was hot-pressed. Tin was melted to form alloy with copper, but copper and carbide former metal were not melted. They were sintered in solid state. The effects of the carbide former metal addition are shown in Table 1. It was concluded that only titanium addition was effective for the improvement of current wear properties, but other carbide former metal was not effective.

Fig. 6 shows the schematic process for TiC products. In this way, titanium diffuses through plated copper and arrives at the carbon fiber surface to form TiC by the reaction with carbon fiber. Fig. 7 shows the results of X-ray analysis of titanium for the composite which were added 3 % titanium by weight in the matrix metal. It proves the existence of TiC around the carbon fiber. By this TiC formation, bonding force of carbon fiber with matrix metal was strengthened, so that carbon fiber didn't easily fly away from the composite even when matrix metal was melted by spark generation. This principle is illustrated in Fig. 8.

The optimum addition amount of titanium was then studied. Fig. 9 shows wear rate as a function of titanium content of matrix bronze metal. As shown in Fig. 9, wear rate under current conditions decreased with increase of titanium content in the matrix. However, as shown in Fig. 10, high titanium content made the composite more porous. Therefore it was suitable for the composite to have about 3 to 5 % titanium in the matrix metal. Based on these studies, we made the carbon fiber/Cu-Sn composite which had 40 % carbon fiber by volume and had 3 % titanium by weight in bronze matrix metal. The results of the wear test for this specimen under continuous 30 min running are shown in Fig. 11. It is evident that wear rate of composite decreased by titanium addition about one order of magnitude under current condition.

CONCLUSIONS

We studied tribology of carbon fiber /Cu-Sn composites and obtained following conclusions.

- (1) Both friction coefficient and wear rate decreased with increase of carbon fiber content in the composite material under no-current conditions.
- (2) When the current was applied, wear rate of the composite increased extremely.
- (3) The effective improvement of these properties was obtained by the addition of titanium in the matrix metal, so as to strengthen the bonding force between carbon fiber and matrix metal.
- (4) The optimum titanium content in matrix metal was about 3 to 5 % by weight.

REFERENCE

- 1 Giltrow J.P. and Lawcaster J.K., "Friction and Wear Properties of Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Metals", *Wear*, vol. 12, May 1968, 91 - 105.
- 2 Amateau M.F. et al, "Friction and Wear Behavior of Metal Matrix-Graphite Fiber Composites", ATR-75(9450)-3, The Aerospace Corp, El Segundo, California, May 1975
- 3 Amateau M.F., "The Effect of Sliding Time and Speed on the Wear of Composite Materials", *Wear*, vol 63, 1980, 121 - 130
- 4 Amateau M.F., "Tribological Behavior of Metal Matrix Composites", TR-0079(4762-03)-1, The Aerospace Corp, El Segundo, California, September 1979.
- 5 Flowers R.H. and Amateau M.F., "High Speed Tribological Properties of Graphite Fiber/Cu-Sn Matrix Composites", *Wear*, vol 49, 1978, 119 - 133.
- 6 Amateau M.F., "On the Effect of Fiber Orientation on the Wear of Composite Materials", *Wear*, vol 53, 1979, 387 - 389

7 Eliezer Z, Khanna V.D. and Amateau M.F., "Wear Mechanism in Composites: a Qualitative model", Wear, vol 51, 1978, 169 - 179.

8 Rylander H.G. and Eliezer Z., "Friction and Wear Properties of Two Types of Copper-Graphite Brushes under severe Sliding Conditions", Wear, vol 50, 1978, 371 - 381.

Table 1. Effects of the carbide former metal additions

	CARBIDE FORMER METAL	CARBIDE TO BE FORMED	RESULTS
1	Fe	Fe ₃ C	CF soluted in Fe.
2	Mo	Mo ₂ C	Carbide wasn't formed in solid state.
3	Al	Al ₄ C ₃	Poor formability. Al ₄ C ₃ hydrolyzed.
4	Ni	Ni ₃ C	Ni soluted in CF.
5	Cr	Cr ₃ C ₂ etc.	Uniform carbide wasn't formed.
6	W	W ₂ C etc.	Carbide wasn't formed in solid state.
7	Ti	TiC	Uniform carbide was formed.

Fig. 1 Cross section of copper plated carbon fiber (0.8 μm thick)

Fig. 2 Cross section of CF/Cu-Sn composite

Fig. 3 Wear rate as a function of carbon fiber content under condition of cycles of 5 sec contact followed by 5 sec non-contact

Fig. 4 Coefficient of friction and heat generation as a function of carbon fiber content under condition of cycles of 5 sec contact followed by 5 sec non-contact

Fig. 5 Wear rate of the composite having 40 % carbon fiber content by volume as a function of sliding velocity under condition of continuous 30 min contact

Fig. 6 Carbide formation by titanium migration

Fig. 7 Titanium distribution in CFRM (by XMA)

Fig. 8 Improvement of resistance to sparks

Fig. 9 Wear rate of the composite as a function of titanium content of matrix bronze metal under condition of 200A at cycles of 1 sec contact followed by 1 sec non-contact with sliding velocity of 100 km/hr

Fig. 10 The percentage of porosity as a function of titanium content of matrix bronze metal

Fig. 11 Wear rate of the composite having 40 % carbon fiber content by volume as a function of sliding velocity under condition of continuous 30 min contact